

Latencies measured with pulsed DPOAE

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Abstract. Level and frequency dependence of ABR latency is thought to depend primarily on cochlear travelling-wave delay. Here, we present measurements of the nonlinear-distortion component of short-pulsed distortion-product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAE) yielding a direct estimator of intracochlear travelling-wave build-up by recording the time elapsed between the f_2 -primary stimulus and the distortion-product pulse response. Thus, this technique avoids to derive latency from phase gradients of the DPOAE coherent-reflection component of different frequencies, as is done using swept-tone DPOAE or SFOAE.

Generally consistent with literature, at low stimulus levels ($L_2 = 35$ dB SPL), DPOAE latency was found to be ≈ 13 ms at $f_2 = 1$ kHz and drops exponentially to ≈ 2 ms at $f_2 = 12 \dots 14$ kHz. Converted to periods of f_2 , the numbers rise from about 13 periods at 1 kHz to > 25 periods above 6 kHz. Between 3 and 6 kHz there is a steeper rise in latency departing from a pure exponential relation between latency and frequency. Dependence of periods on level is -7% per 10 dB level increase. Stability of latencies over the seven visits was high: The median of absolute differences between visits was < 1 period for all frequencies except 14 kHz. Level dependence of the latency was surprisingly variable between subjects. Some perfectly normal-hearing subjects show only a -2% change in latency per 10 dB level increase, others showed a dependence of -12% per 10 dB level increase. Test-retest accuracy of latency determination with short-pulsed DPOAE was found to be high. Comparison with auditory-brainstem response literature leaves some discrepancy unresolved.

INTRODUCTION

Within a framework of linear minimum-phase systems, latency of a signal to reach its characteristic place in the cochlea bears a fixed relationship to frequency tuning [1, 2]: sharper tuning is achievable only with longer latencies. In animal experiments, it has been shown that basilar-membrane and auditory-nerve tuning curves show almost identical tuning [3, 4], and this directly connects cochlear latency to bandwidth (or some Q-factor) of psychophysical tuning curves which can be measured in humans [5, 6]. At the same time, the current concept of the so-called cochlear amplifier and related experimental work in mammals has established the principle that the more gain the cochlear amplifier adds pre-neurally, the sharper the frequency tuning becomes, thus relating frequency tuning to threshold [1]. This latter relation is also reflected in mathematical models of cochlear traveling-wave generation that include an active feedback mechanism [7, 8, 9], and, in a model with a realistic middle-ear representation, such models typically comprise a concurrent change of threshold and frequency tuning from low to high frequencies [9].

Studies of frequency-dependence of OAE and related neural latencies in animals and humans recently focused on deviations from a simple power law which could be described by one exponent only [10, 11]. Specifically, in humans, a "break" in continuity is suggested in latency measurements of OAE at about 1 kHz [11], and a second break at about 2.5 kHz [12]. The latter two investigations based their latency measure on the group delay of stimulus-frequency otoacoustic emissions (SFOAE). This method has to rely on the phase gradient of OAE, thus requiring measurements at different frequencies (typically realized by sweeping the stimulus frequency) which can bring about peculiar problems – at least in individual measurements – due to e.g. place-dependent condition of the amplifier as well as the open question to what extent the hypothesized relation of group delay to latency depends on the measurement criteria taking into account the nonlinearity of the system under test. Apart from that, studies including ABR measurements [13, 14, 15] appear not to support clearly all reported breaks in continuity. Recently, in a test-retest study we gathered short-pulsed DPOAE data in 10 normal-hearing subjects in the frequency range 1...14 kHz. From these data, the latency of the $2f_1 - f_2$ nonlinear-distortion component of the DPOAE can be directly obtained in the time domain. Here, we show frequency and level dependence of DPOAE latency and compare with DPOAE and SFOAE data based on the phase-gradient method.

METHODS

DPOAE data shown here stem from a published study analysing properties other than latency [16, 17]. In brief, DPOAE were measured with an Etymotic ER-10C system, a National Instruments data acquisition card, and customary software. Calibration was performed in-ear, and sound-pressure level at the tympanic membrane was estimated by using a correction based on an artificial ear compliant with IEC 60318-4. Short-pulsed DPOAE were recorded for $1 \leq f_2 \leq 14$ kHz with $f_2/f_1 = 1.2$. Time responses of the isolated $2f_1 - f_2$ distortion product were extracted using the primary-tone phase variation technique [18] by shifting the f_1, f_2 stimulus tones by 90° and 180° in consecutive blocks, with additional digital filtering. These DPOAE pulse responses comprise – if existent – both, the nonlinear-distortion (ND) and the coherent-reflection (CR) component of the DPOAE. Seven stimulus pulse pairs are organized in an interlaced arrangement within one block, and two such blocks are used to cover 14 frequencies. We used a f_2 short-pulse stimulus, i.e. the f_1 -pulse was presented for a duration between 20 and 40 ms, whereas the duration of the f_2 -pulse was chosen shorter dependent on frequency to induce pulse responses where the ND and the CR component are clearly separated in time, i.e., the ND component already decays when the longer-latency CR component comes in. The low-latency, ND component of the DPOAE is extracted with an onset-decomposition (OD) algorithm sampling the pulse-response waveform close to the point of having reached the steady state of the ND component, τ_{OD} , thus avoiding interference due to the CR component (for a detailed description, see [19], methods D.3). 10 different levels in 5 dB-steps were presented, where the lowest L_2 -level was 25...35 dB SPL, depending on frequency. The stimulus levels of the first primary, L_1 , were chosen, where possible, as the individually optimal combinations, based on the projection of the ridge of a separately measured DPOAE level map to the L_2, L_1 plane [16]. Pulse responses had to fulfill a $SNR \geq 10$ dB and pass a χ^2 test qualifying its reproducibility.

Latencies are defined in the time waveform as $\tau = \tau_{OD} - \tau_{f_2, on}$, where $\tau_{f_2, on}$ is the time when the f_2 -pulse has reached its steady state, or as periods of the second primary, N_{f_2} . When fits to experimental latency data in periods of f_2 are computed, period-vs-frequency dependence scaled double-logarithmically was formulated as follows:

$$\Gamma(20\log_{10}(f_2)) = 20\log_{10}(N_{f_2}) = c_1 + c_2 20\log_{10}(f_2) + c_3(-L_2/100) + \frac{c_4}{2}(\tanh(c_5 20\log_{10}(f_2/c_6))) \quad (1)$$

where $c_i, i = 1...6$, are the model parameters. The first three parameters $c_{1...3}$ correspond to the parameters b, c , and d of the formulation of Neely et al. [13] and Rasetswhane et al. [15], by the formulae $c_1 = 20\log_{10}(b)$, $c_2 = 1 - d$, and $c_3 = 20\log_{10}(c)$. The model function is fitted to experimental data using the matlab function `lsqnonlin`.

RESULTS

Figure 1 shows mean values of latencies as a function of frequency and stimulus level across all ears and visits, expressed as periods of the second primary frequency, N_{f_2} , in double-logarithmic scaling. Mean latencies are 10 and 17 ms at 1 kHz and decrease in a negative exponential manner to values of around 2 ms at 14 kHz, corresponding to the range of 22...34 periods seen in the Figure 1. In terms of periods, the data show an almost monotonic and, in terms of $\Gamma(20\log_{10}(f_2))$, roughly linear growth up to 14 kHz, corresponding to more than a doubling of the periods over the measured frequency range. In more detail, we discern that between approximately 3 and 6 kHz, the slope of the period rise appears consistently steeper than at lower and higher frequencies. The bottom panel shows the same data marked with crosses, along with a fit according to Equation 1 which approximates the steeper rise in the mid-frequency region with a \tanh . Independent of frequency, high sound-pressure levels systematically lead to shorter latencies than low-level stimuli. With respect to level-dependence, it might be noted that it appears more regular (almost equal spacing of the lines) at intermediate stimulus levels. Especially at the lowest measured levels, the latencies tend to depart toward exceptionally high latencies.

When we fitted all latencies in units of [ms] dependent on frequency f_2 in [kHz], i.e., without accounting for level-dependence, the exponent of the frequency dependence was -0.701 ± 0.003 . Scaled in periods, the exponent is then 0.299. Fitting with the first three terms of Equation 1, the exponent of the frequency dependence of the periods was $c_2 = 0.338$, and with all six terms, $c_2 = 0.259$ (Table 1), the difference being due to the fact that part of the increase with frequency is taken up by the \tanh function when fitting with all six terms. All fit parameters were significant at $p \leq 0.05$ (two-sided t-test on whether a parameter is different from zero). The overall quality of the fit is high, the standard deviation of the residuals was $SD_{lin} = 1.406$ dB, corresponding to 1.18 periods, for the linear fit (three terms), and $SD_{log} = 1.069$ dB, corresponding to 1.13 periods, for the nonlinear fit (six terms). Relative to the overall mean

FIGURE 1. Short-pulsed DPOAE latencies of the ND component expressed in periods of f_2 , dependent on level and frequency. The upper panel shows the mean values across ears and visits, depending on frequency and level. Each color represents a stimulus sound pressure, ranging $25 \leq L_2 \leq 80$ dB SPL (from dark blue to cyan). Starting and ending of the model fit lines (bottom panel) at intermediate frequencies reflects that starting levels were chosen dependent on frequency range to optimize data collection efficiency (see methods). The mean values of the experimental data are marked by crosses.

TABLE 1. Fitting parameters c_i according to Equation 1 along with their standard error (SE), for two fits: when using all 6 terms, and when using only the first three terms of the equation. b , c , d are the correspondent parameters as used in [13, 15].

i	c_i	$\pm SE$	$c_i, i = 1...3$	SE	b [ms], d, c
1	24.9	0.207	23.9	0.223	15.7
2	0.259	0.014	0.338	0.0091	0.662
3	6.283	0.194	6.196	0.353	2.041
4	1.375	0.214			
5	0.823	0.337			
6	4.718	0.134			

value of 21.4 periods, the standard deviation corresponds to a 17.6% change for the linear fit, and for the nonlinear fit according to Equation 1 13.1%.

Test-retest reliability of the latency results over the 7 visits covering 3 months was generally high. Figure 2 shows four examples of individual level dependences, where the upper both panels show a deviation from the dependence seen typically on one of the both ears: For subject 1, $f_2 = 2$ kHz, the left ear (blueish lines) show only a very shallow level dependence, for subject 2, $f_2 = 4$ kHz, the side with the shallow dependence is the right ear (reddish lines). In

FIGURE 2. Four examples of level-dependent latencies. Upper left panel: For subject 1, at $f_2 = 2$ kHz, the left ear (blueish lines) shows only a shallow level dependence, notwithstanding that hearing threshold is 9 dB HL, whereas the right ear shows a typical dependence. Upper right panel: For subject 2, at $f_2 = 4$ kHz, the right ear shows a shallow dependence, notwithstanding that hearing threshold is -4 dB HL, whereas the left ear behaves typical (reddish lines).

the bottom left panel, a typical example with similar latency dependence on both sides is shown ($f_2 = 6$ kHz), in the bottom right panel, an example at ($f_2 = 14$ kHz) where for the left ear, the level dependence is as expected, although with more scatter than in the other examples, and for the right ear with scatter which for some visits precludes detection of the level dependence at all.

DISCUSSION

In this study, frequency-dependence of the latency of the ND component of the DPOAE in the range of 1...14 kHz follows roughly a power law with an exponent of $-0.66... - 0.71$. Correspondingly, the frequency-dependence of the periods has an exponent of $0.29...0.34$, which may be regarded as a proxy for the increase in gain and frequency tuning of the cochlear amplifier observed from apex to base. The range of the above-mentioned numbers reflects different weighting of residuals depending on whether the fit is performed with delays in [ms] or [dB re. period].

Figure 3 compares latency functions from this study to selected data from the literature for a relatively low stimulation level of 35–40 dB SPL, including SFOAE [20, 21] and DPOAE reflection source measurements [21], along with a latency function derived from TEOAE stimulated with 61 dB peSPL [22]. This dependence almost exactly matches the exponent of the frequency-dependence for behavioral frequency-tuning in a forward masking task expressed as tuning-quality factor $Q_{erb}(f)$ of 0.27, as found in [5] for frequencies of 1–8 kHz. The overall trend of these OAE latency measures and their comparison to psychophysical tuning estimates thus is in line with the view that frequency selectivity in the auditory nerve and thus related psychophysical performance is basically provided by the mechanical frequency selectivity of the cochlear filter, at least at low levels, as was also shown in a single preparation in Chinchilla for an apical location [4], and that the cochlea and the following neural signal processing provides filtering close to the minimum-phase theorem for linear filtering, as has been proposed a long time ago [23].

In earlier literature, sometimes scale invariance has been postulated, at least for the basal part of the cochlea; today, the term "approximate local scaling invariance" might be more appropriate and be defined by an exponent of the

FIGURE 3. Comparison of latencies to the literature. Abbreviated source, stimulus level, and measurement type are given in the legend. OAE data are shown as blueish curves. The continuous blue curve represents our mean data at 40 dB SPL, the three other lines (MS16, AGS18) are derived by time-frequency analysis or the phase-gradient method. The green line represents Q_{erb} data derived from psycho-physical tuning curves (LOS22), the both reddish curves derive from tone-burst ABR wave-V (TB-ABR, RAS13) and narrow-band action potential data (NAP, E79). The black, dashed line represents a slope of Γ of 0.3 dB/dB.

frequency-dependence of Γ being below 0.3. $2^{0.3} = 1.23$ means that over the range of one octave, properties such as filter bandwidth or latency change "only" by 23%, which might be taken as the – always arbitrary – limit to speak of approximate local scaling invariance. In this sense, the region between $f_2 = 3...6$ kHz would appear to clearly violate approximate local scaling symmetry.

However, these deviations from a simple power law are not in accordance with deviations which have been found and discussed by others. Christensen et al. [12] found a second break at 2.6 kHz, from where onwards the increase over frequency of DPOAE "scaled" phase – a method to reduce the influence of the different frequency ratios they used – is much reduced, and also a break in the corresponding SFOAE measure, which however, contrary to their DPOAE data, steepens above that transition frequency. Rescaling the data of the example shown in Fig. 5 of Christensen as $\Gamma(\log(f))$, a segmented straight fit to the SFOAE data would probably break at 350 Hz (clearly) and at 1.5 kHz (weakly), and overall the curve shows more continuous curvature than clearly identifiable breaks. If one scales their DPOAE latency logarithmically, i.e. as Γ , the clearest feature is a break at a frequency of around 4 kHz, above which Γ stays almost constant. If we compare to log-log scaled mean curves recorded at sound pressure levels at 40 dB SPL to those based on stimulus-frequency OAE (SFOAE) data from [20, 21] as well as CR component DPOAE group-delay data [21], we could be tempted to identify various weak breaks in their curves above 1 kHz, but there is certainly no common feature in the range of 1...5 kHz, where all curves of the above-mentioned authors provide data. To conclude on the issue of scaling breaks, it appears that the salient common feature of the four methods from which one would expect to be able to infer something about cochlear scaling, is a rather constant rise in periods of around 0.3 dB/dB throughout the range of 1...10 kHz.

CONCLUSION

The general frequency dependence of the ND component DPOAE latency derived by analysing pulse responses in the time domain matched well with the results known from the literature examining the CR component of SFOAE and DPOAE with the phase-gradient method and might be summarized as following approximately a 0.3 dB/dB rise in periods with frequency. Breaks in the scaling law other than the so-called apical-basal break which lies at the lower end of the frequencies investigated here and, therefore, cannot be safely identified in the present data, are not in agreement with those found by others. Scaling symmetry may be violated at least in individual subjects in certain frequency regions even in the presence of perfectly normal hearing thresholds, if one is to set the limit to correspond to a frequency exponent of 0.3.

The inconsistency between ABR latencies and OAE latencies at frequencies ≥ 4 kHz remains unresolved, ABR latencies appear to generally predict higher latencies than OAE. Moreover, on the individual level, in some exceptional cases, high latencies appear to be not necessary to reach excellent hearing threshold, a property which might violate the minimum-phase predictions and warrant model studies to mimick such effects.

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COMMENTS & QUESTIONS

[**A. Tichacek:**] In the beginning of your talk you were showing the shift in the level maps for different individuals [Dalhoff, off records: ...shift of the ridge of a level map, with other words, the optimal stimulus path]. Is this because there is a difference in tuning of the cochlear filters?

[**E. Dalhoff:**] I can't explain but my intuition is that since this seems not to be connected with individual threshold, it is probably an expression of the individual middle-ear transfer function which also might not be so ultra-smooth that there are no perturbations of the group-mean optimal path.

[**P. Martin:**] In the plot of latencies versus frequency and level, there seems to be at low levels a plateau of the latency just below 10 kHz. How does this compare to neural measurements, is there a discrepancy?

[**E. Dalhoff:**] We did not measure psychophysically or with DPOAE suppression measurements filter bandwidth of our subjects. But generally, of course, It is known that the tendency is that they become sharper at lower sound pressure levels, that means with higher gain.

[**P. Martin:**] So, it is consistent with what we know.

[**E. Dalhoff:**] Yes, in the group mean in any case.